

An Roinn Oideachais
Department of Education

Institiúid Oideachais
Institute of Education

Numeracy Integration across Primary and Post-Primary Curricula

A Review of the Literature

**Prepared by Thérèse Dooley and Miriam Ryan, Institute of
Education, Dublin City University, for the Department of
Education**

Author Note

Thérèse Dooley <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5671-4075>

Miriam Ryan <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0484-4211>

Suggested Citation

Dooley, T. & Ryan, M. (2022). *Numeracy integration across primary and post-primary curricula. A review of the literature*. Department of Education (Ireland).

Summary

The aim of this report is to examine how best numeracy can be integrated in a meaningful way across the primary and post-primary curriculum. The review is guided by the following research questions:

1. What benefits potentially accrue to integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?
2. What factors underpin effective integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?
3. What are the challenges to effective integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?

We found 13 articles relevant to our question. There was a paucity of literature on the development of numeracy across curricular subjects in our search. However, we found examples of other models of integration - STEM/STEAM, integration of two or more subjects (“content-and subject-based integration”), and Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) - which were pertinent for our research questions. The following findings emerged:

- Numeracy can be understood from “basic skills”, “problem-solving” and “critical” perspectives. The latter two perspectives in particular benefit effective integration across the curriculum.
- Different forms of integration meet different learning goals. Transdisciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches are endorsed in the literature as enhancing student learning.
- Integration of numeracy across the curriculum has clear potential to benefit primary and post-primary students’ learning. For example, STEM/STEAM education has positive effects on student creativity, and brings about improved performance in assessed learning outcomes, including “non-traditional” outcomes such as increased student collaboration and the provision of opportunities for community involvement. With regard to subject- and content-based integration, improved learning outcomes have been noted with integrating mathematics in a wide number of areas. CLIL has been found to enhance learning in a content area and in the language of instruction.
- Problem/project-based learning and problem posing are pedagogical approaches to integration of numeracy across the curriculum that support high-quality learning by primary and post-primary students.
- Integration can be superficial in nature unless there is respect by teachers for all subjects concerned and specific learning goals are identified around all disciplines being integrated. Authentic assessment focused on evaluating learners’ success in achieving all learning intentions is warranted.
- A supportive environment includes commitment from management to the ideas and principles of integrated learning, a recognition by teachers of the academic status of different subjects and an openness among them to communicate with other disciplines.
- Challenges to effective integration include teachers’ poor understanding of and negative attitude towards the process, lack of interrogation of and explication of learning outcomes across all subjects concerned, and assessments targeting monodisciplinary rather than interdisciplinary knowledge.

The review is limited by the small number of studies that met our criteria for inclusion. Neither did we include early years’ settings. We expect that with an increased focus on the

integration of numeracy across the curriculum both in Ireland and across other jurisdictions, relevant findings around benefits and underpinnings of and challenges to the process will emerge.

Recommendations

Pillar 1: Enabling parents and communities to support children's literacy and numeracy development

- Schools should explore the community as a context for the rich and meaningful development of numeracy by students. (McDonald & Smith, 2020; Merritt et al., 2017; White & Delaney, 2021)
- Schools should draw on and facilitate interaction with individuals/organisations in the community who can demonstrate their everyday use of numeracy. (Belbase et al., 2021; White & Delaney, 2021)

Pillar 2: Teachers' and Early Childhood Care and Education practitioners' professional practice

- Educators need to develop an understanding of ways in which different approaches to integration meet different educational goals. An understanding of how “problem-solving” and “critical” numeracy can enhance or be enhanced through their own and other subject areas should be part of the discussion. (Askew, 2015; Belbase et al., 2021; Carter et al., 2015; Geiger, Forgasz, & Goos, 2015; Perignat & Katz-Buonincontro, 2019; White & Delaney, 2021)
- Educators should have the opportunity to develop relevant subject knowledge of the disciplines being integrated, including concepts, skills and processes (McKinney et al., 2014).
- Planning for integrated learning should include a focus on learning outcomes of all subjects involved, including numeracy goals. Outcomes that extend beyond the cognitive domain to include affective and interpersonal components should be considered. Learning activities should be carefully planned with regard to their potential to promote learning in all subjects involved. (Ahlskog-Björkman & Björklund, 2016; Belbase et al., 2021; Gao et al., 2020; White & Delaney, 2021)

Pillar 3: Building the capacity of early years'/school leadership

- School leaders at all levels should be afforded the resources and time to enable them to address the complexity of the meaningful integration of numeracy. Expertise in conceptualising the models of integration in use, and in identifying opportunities and methods for integration across the range of subjects should be developed. (Carter et al., 2015; McKinney et al., 2014)

Pillar 4: Curriculum and the learning experience

- The use of problem-/project-based learning and problem posing perspectives as a methodology in the integration of all subjects with numeracy is recommended. Educators should identify problems that are meaningful and relevant to learners' lives and that offer scope for problem-based learning and problem-posing experiences. (Bennison, 2015; McDonald & Smith, 2020; Merritt et al., 2017)
- Curriculum documentation should draw attention to and provide examples of effective integration of numeracy across the curriculum, such as CLIL (including immersion approaches), STEM/STEAM and its many modifications, subject- and content-based integration. (Carter et al., 2015; McKinney et al., 2014)
- Classroom spaces and timetabling that are conducive to an integrated approach should be provided. (Belbase et al., 2021)

Pillar 6: Assessment and evaluation to support learning in literacy and numeracy

- Forms of assessment which give due regard to learning outcomes in component disciplinary areas of cross-curricular integration should be devised. Authentic assessment which evaluates learners' success in achieving integrated learning intentions is required. (Gao et al., 2020)

Numeracy: Integration across Primary and Post-Primary Curricula

In the DES (2011) strategy, a particular emphasis was placed on the development of numeracy (and literacy) across the curriculum:

Learning in many curricular areas provides a rich context for the development of literacy and numeracy skills. Literacy and numeracy activity can become contextualised, meaningful and purposeful to the learner through many subjects and areas of learning. We know that the development of literacy and numeracy skills also complements learning in other areas of the curriculum... Good numeracy skills are important for learning across the curriculum in terms of equipping learners with contextual and strategic know-how including attributes such as the confidence to have a go, make mistakes and try again that can also benefit learning in other areas. (DES, 2011, p.46)

While the 2011 strategy has resulted in improved performance by primary and post-primary students in mathematics, the integration of numeracy across curricular areas was highlighted as an area of concern in the interim report (DES, 2017):

It has been suggested, in the consultation process, that the integration of literacy and numeracy across the full primary curriculum needs further support and resources made available to support for example, teachers, incorporating numeracy in arts, geography or PE classes. This will help children to see aspects of literacy and numeracy as part of their everyday lives without in any way diminishing the time or richness of such other curricular areas. (p.36)

There are no such concerns expressed about the integration of numeracy across the post-primary curriculum. However, one of the recommendations made in the report that it is an area that needs further attention:

... best practice subject-specific literacy and numeracy (including reasoning and problem solving) skills and digital literacy are embedded in all new specifications in Junior and Senior cycle and that this approach is emphasised in teachers' professional learning to support these. (p.59)

An issue that mitigates against the integration of numeracy across the curriculum is the interpretation of numeracy. It has now evolved from a "basic skills" perspective, and

embraces both a problem-solving view, i.e., related to the ability to use mathematical skills and understanding to solve complex problems and meets the demands of day-to-day living and the more recent critical orientation, i.e., where learners are engaged in thinking critically about the use of mathematics in the world, the power inherent in mathematics, and the effect of this power on themselves and others (Askew, 2015). The contingent nature of “problem-solving” numeracy leads to the widespread recognition that numeracy learning should take place in many contexts and across all school subjects (Geiger et al., 2015). Askew (2015), placing an emphasis on the critical orientation to numeracy, suggests that one of the ways it can be developed is the questioning by learners of the role that mathematics plays in supporting societal or political values in particular contexts.

Also revealed in the literature is a range of conceptualisations of integration with associated implications for planning and learning. Integration of different areas is intended to forge strong connections across disciplines, content and contexts to enhance and enrich the overall learning experience and to help children develop a rounded understanding of the integrated world they inhabit. Cross-curricular integration can be approached in a number of different ways (Perignat & Katz-Buonincontro, 2019; White & Delaney, 2021):

- Transdisciplinary integration includes fully merged disciplines without boundaries and lessons rooted in authentic problems or inquiry;
- Interdisciplinary integration brings several disciplines together under a common theme, but each discipline remains discrete;
- Multidisciplinary integration includes collaboration among two or more disciplines but are not merged;
- Cross-disciplinary integration focuses on observing one discipline through the perspective of another, for example, the physics of music.

Given varying conceptualisations and definitions of both numeracy and integration, it is hardly surprising that embedding numeracy across all subjects is identified in the DES interim report as an issue that needs further attention. Teachers’ awareness of these conceptualisations and how they might address different educational goals is critical if deep and meaningful integration of numeracy across the curriculum is to be enacted.

The aim of this report is to examine how best numeracy can be integrated in a meaningful way across the primary and post-primary curriculum in a way that supports learners’ numeracy development as well as enhancing, and without any ill effect on, all

subject areas. We do this against a background of endorsement for cross-curricular integration in relevant policy documents in Ireland. For example, in the research reports developed to underpin the proposed new primary mathematics curriculum (Dooley et al., 2014; Dooley, 2019), it is highlighted as a key practice in the teaching of mathematics. Cross-curricular integration also receives considerable attention in the draft specification of the primary curriculum (NCCA, 2020). The Department of Education and Science (DES) *STEM Education Policy Statement 2017-2026* sets out recommendations and areas for action to enhance STEM education experience and outcomes for learners from early years to post-primary school (DES, 2017). Furthermore, Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) is represented in immersion education in the Irish educational system and the newer focus on short courses at Junior Cycle (the first three years of post-primary education). We expect that the cross-curricular integration of numeracy will support and be supported by initiatives such as these.

The review we conducted was guided by the following research questions:

1. What benefits potentially accrue to integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?
2. What factors underpin effective integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?
3. What are the challenges to effective integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?

As detailed in the appendix, 13 articles relevant to our question emerged from our systematic review. There was a paucity of literature on the development of numeracy across curricular subjects in our search. However, we found examples of other models of integration, the findings of which are pertinent for our research questions. The majority of these articles (five) dealt with STEM/STEAM education, two articles focused on the use of problems as an approach to integration, one centred on numeracy, one was based on Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), and four addressed the integration of two or more subjects (Mathematics and Physical Education (PE), Mathematics and Social Justice, Mathematics and Nutrition Education, Science and Religion education) - examples such as these four will be referred to hereon as “subject- and content-based integration”. In the narrative report below, we present an overview of these findings, potential benefits, underpinnings and challenges, on the basis of which we draw conclusions for cross-curricular numeracy development.

Narrative Report

Models of Integration

STEM/ STEAM Education: Potential Benefits, and Underpinnings

The phrase "STEM education" is used to describe a focus on pedagogy related to and student learning within Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) fields. In its original conception it concerned distinct STEM disciplines, there is now a greater emphasis on integrated learning of STEM disciplines in order that students/graduates are able to solve complex real-world problems. STEAM Education, which involves an incorporation of ARTS into STEM Education, was a later development, which arose in response to a need for creativity and innovation in the solutions to these complex real-world problems. STEM/STEAM education is usually considered from a transdisciplinary or interdisciplinary perspective, as these perspectives are most conducive to integrated learning (Perignat & Katz-Buonincontro, 2019; White & Delaney, 2021). While STEAM Education is the predominant modification of STEM, there is a range of others, e.g., eSTEM (i.e, STEM education with a strong digital and technology focus); STEAM by design (STEAM education that occurs within a "Place base project" paradigm); STREAM (critical reading and/or writing, combined with STEAM) (White & Delaney, 2021). Belbase et al. (2021) concluded their documentary analysis of STEAM education by calling for 'h' to be added to the acronym (STEAM-h) "where the 'h' stands for humanity to care for environmental balance for a sustainable future." (p.27). What this seems to suggest is that what is critical for learners is that there is an emphasis on integration across *all* subjects so that they are prepared to deal with real-life problems both at present and in the future.

Aguilera et al. (2021) found, albeit on the basis of limited evidence, that both STEM and STEAM had positive effects on student creativity - however, creativity is generally associated with STEAM rather than STEM projects. In the review conducted by White and Delaney (2021), it was found that the implementation of STEM/STEAM results in improved performance in assessed learning outcomes such as greater achievement in comparable testing, and awards, and enhanced participation in relevant academic pursuits. In addition, they suggest that the STEM/STEAM interdisciplinary platform could potentially enhance a range of other "non-traditional" outcomes such as the use of real-world contexts in teaching and learning, increased student collaboration, as well as the provision of opportunities for community involvement and interaction with individuals employed in STEM-related careers.

Common educational threads for the successful implementation of STEM/STEAM education were community collaboration and involvement and, not surprisingly, the use of problem-based learning (PBL) and project-based learning (PjBL).

Both PBL and PjBL involve students learning content by actively and collaboratively solving authentic, real-world problems but PjBL is usually more associated with an end product and with instructional guidance than is PBL (Edmunds et al., 2017). Belbase et al. (2021) also found that problem-based learning (PBL) and problem-solving scenarios are an effective means of implementing STEAM Education. Problem-solving scenarios are those in which “students get a context with foregrounded problems... they use their creativity and critical thinking in collaborative ways using group dynamics to initiate the problems, reword them, plan the course of actions with alternatives, and examine each option” (Belbase et al., 2021, p. 17). Merritt et al. (2017) - who conducted a review of the effectiveness of PBL (which they describe as encompassing PjBL) in Science and Mathematics for K-8 students - argue that the problems used in this approach range from highly unstructured to structured. They found that younger learners tended to be presented with more structured problems and to be given more guidance in the problem-solving process. Unstructured problems were generally used in studies involving older primary or post-primary students - such problems are characterised by their lack of structure, meaning that students have to generate ideas in order to identify issues and approaches related to a particular case or scenario. Merritt et al. conclude that the literacy abilities of students need to be taken into account when deciding on suitable problem types for use in PBL. They also found that student-centred learning opportunities helped to improve four skills, that is problem-solving, cooperative skills, communication skills and technology skills (with less emphasis in studies on the latter two). PBL was found to have positive effects on students’ academic achievement, knowledge retention, conceptual development, and attitudes. Noteworthy is the fact that although Merritt et al. were interested in PBL as it related to mathematics and science, all studies that were screened by them focused on science. Furthermore, most studies involved students in K6-8, despite evidence cited by the authors that younger students can benefit from a PBL approach.

McDonald and Smith (2020) conducted a review on the benefits for learners of using mathematical problem-posing in the curriculum (specifically, for them, the Curriculum for Excellence in Scotland). They draw on the definition of problem posing furnished by Stoyanova and Ellerton (1996, p. 518), that is “the process by which, on the basis of

mathematical experience, students construct personal interpretations of concrete situations and formulate them as meaningful mathematical problems”. As described above for PBL, problem posing can stem from very unstructured, semi-structured and structured situations. McDonald and Smith found problem posing was associated with increased motivation, creativity and engagement at primary level, and with improved mathematical achievement, positive attitude towards and increased interest in mathematics and improved motivation to engage in mathematics at post-primary level. There was evidence that problem-posing interventions brought about an improvement in both problem-posing and problem-solving skills. Mathematical problem posing is not without its challenges, however - some that are highlighted in the review are the difficulties that learners experience in posing contextualised or sensible problems and identifying salient information in solving problem/semantic issues. McDonald and Smith also found that learners were more inclined to engage in problems that they found relevant to their lives and interests, and they noted the importance of group work and reflection in the problem-posing process. As discussed by Bennison (2015), such problems can arise from subjects across the curriculum. Examples of these are described in the section on subject- and content-based integration below.

STEM/STEAM Education: Challenges.

While STEM/STEAM has been shown to have a positive impact on students’ learning, motivation and creativity, it is not without its challenges. There are a number of logistical challenges particularly for transdisciplinary and interdisciplinary collaboration, e.g., common space for support materials, time for planning, and class/subject timetabling that facilitates the process (Belbase et al., 2021). Issues of implementation are strongly connected to teachers’ individual content knowledge, as well as their beliefs about learning, the content areas themselves, and the purpose and utility of integration. Belbase et al. (2021) suggest that one of the greatest of the challenges associated with the implementation of STEAM is the pre-existing conception by many educators and students that “STEM” and “Arts” cannot support one another in a meaningful way. This may be due to teachers either failing to see interdisciplinary connections or having a single disciplinary focus. Teachers can have different values and beliefs that can hinder the integration process. There can also be a lack of agreement about the aims of an integrated approach, e.g., whether to integrate processes or content. Gao et al. (2020) articulate the tension inherent in integrated planning. With a focus on secondary school STEM, they note that planning may be for learning in both disciplines,

or it may be that one discipline serves as a vehicle or tool to advance the learning in another, or indeed the aim can be to help learners develop skills that go beyond a single discipline.

Perignat and Katz-Buonincontro (2019) conclude that while there was a belief among many researchers and educationalists that the 'A' in STEAM allowed for greater creativity, risk-taking etc. there was very little articulation of arts education learning outcomes in the literature they surveyed. At the same time STEM learning seems to be explicitly prioritized over the arts in some articles. They suggest that STEAM should not be conceptualised as STEM with "A added" but rather as a pedagogical approach that gives equal regard to all elements. On the other hand, and as mentioned above, Belbase et al. (2021) argue that mathematics is often overshadowed by the other STEM disciplines, and that, therefore, critical thinking and mathematical reasoning should be made explicit in the design of STEAM projects. It would seem then that the interrogation of and explication of learning outcomes are essential for effective STEAM integration. In this interrogation, attention needs to be given to "non-traditional" outcomes.

With regard to assessment of interdisciplinary STEM learning, the issue of fidelity to and weighting of individual disciplines also arises. Gao et al. (2020) note that education systems often retain the traditional separation of the disciplines notwithstanding the conceptualisation of STEM education as interdisciplinary. The complexity of planning and facilitating integrated STEM lessons and modules is reflected in the challenges in assessing them. Of forty-nine studies on assessment in STEM that they reviewed, nineteen reported assessments in individual disciplines. A mismatch was identified between the stated learning intentions to improve students' interdisciplinary knowledge and skills, and the focus of assessments. Only nine studies attempted to assess interdisciplinary knowledge, though it was noted that these assessments were more diverse and innovative than those with a focus on a single discipline. Most assessments targeted monodisciplinary knowledge, and mono- and transdisciplinary affective issues. Affective issues assessed focused on attitudes, motivation and interests in STEM subjects as a result of engagement in STEM learning, and took the form of questionnaires and surveys. In many cases, the assessments were judged to be more akin to research activity and not compatible with a teacher's focus nor achievable in terms of time required to code and analyse. Belbase et al. (2021) propose that the student-centred, holistic and criterion-based assessment approaches seem most appropriate in the context of

learning in STEAM education and warrant attention in the consideration of school-based assessment of integration.

Subject- and Content-based Integration: Potential Benefits and Underpinnings

While it is certainly the case that the integration of the STEM, and more recently STEAM, subjects has garnered a lot of attention in the public and vernacular discourse, the application of numeracy can enhance learning throughout the curriculum. In this section, messages from the literature on integration of numeracy with other subjects are discussed, and challenges identified. A limited number of subjects has received research attention: this limitation represents a lacuna in the literature rather than lack of potential for integration of numeracy across the curriculum. Improved learning outcomes have been noted with integrating numeracy in areas as diverse as language learning, history and social justice, nutrition education, Physical Education, as well as in the integration of science and religion.

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) aims to enhance learning in a content area and in the language of instruction, and is long present in Ireland in, for example, gaeloideachais contexts (Harris & Ó Duibhir, 2011). In looking at outcomes for language and content learning, Graham et al. (2018) found improved outcomes in at least some aspects of learning for students in 17 out of 25 studies, and equivalent outcomes for the remaining eight studies. In the small number of studies, which focused on mathematics, learners in a CLIL environment outperformed their peers receiving instruction in their first language. Complexities in comparing learning across language environments are acknowledged, with differences in practices on language use in testing and non-equivalent instruction time noted, making comparisons with non-CLIL groups problematic. While Gao (2020) urges integrated assessments for integrated content, best practice in second language education advocates a dual language approach, so that any deficit in language competence is not confused with conceptual understanding (De Villiers, 2015). Recommended approaches might be to offer assessment in both languages of the learner, or to craft assessment tools - perhaps with diagrams or images to replace or support text, so that any language deficit will not preclude the learner from achieving in line with their numeracy competence. Positive findings for students learning through a second language are in line with reports from the all-Irish sector in Ireland (McCoy et al., 2012; Shiel et al., 2011). While CLIL appears to offer benefits in terms of enhanced learning, these do not happen by accident. The importance of planning is highlighted in the careful consideration of the competing demands of language and content

demands required in CLIL. Priorities arising specifically in CLIL include the careful pitching of content to ensure that the language challenges are not beyond the linguistic competence of the learners and that the requirements to negotiate the new content in conjunction with new language demands do not place the working memory of the learner under excessive pressure. These considerations might be considered to parallel in some respects the concerns about the weightings attached to the integrated disciplines raised by Gao et al. (2020).

As mentioned above, benefits of the intersection of mathematics and social justice have been noted. McGee and Hostetler point to the use of mathematics to analyse, quantify and draw conclusions in the service of social justice and history education. The benefits of a mathematical lens in preparing learners for active and informed citizenship are presented and exemplified. Project work on issues such as current and historical issues of disenfranchisement can be enriched by drawing on mathematical skills and tools such as descriptive and analytical statistics. Complex work is involved in planning and facilitating important, though perhaps potentially controversial, issues integrated with numeracy and represents a need and challenge for teachers and school communities who are more likely to have backgrounds of relative privilege to recognise their own biases and assumptions.

Support for teachers in the high-level planning that is necessary for effective integration is echoed by Carter et al. (2014). There are attendant issues of professional development, to facilitate planning and assessment. The need to prepare for integration by putting necessary conditions in place emerged strongly from an initiative to integrate science and religious education at second level. McKinney et al. (2014) note the success of a team approach characterised by respect for the academic status of the disciplines involved. Also required for effective team teaching is a commitment to acquiring the relevant subject knowledge of the other discipline - to include concepts, skills and processes. As such, those schools experiencing success in the integration of science and religious education fulfilled the requirements of support, commitment and collegiality.

Successful outcomes of integration with numeracy are also reported where more pragmatic considerations motivate the integration attempts. Studies on the integration of nutrition education, and Physical Education with numeracy and literacy report positive outcomes to both of these areas, to include greater awareness and understanding of nutrition content, and positive effects of integrated PE and physical education on performance in

standardised test scores, as well as improvements in activity level among pupils (Follong et al., 2021; Martinnen, 2015).

There is, however, a need to consider the depth and level of learning within separate subjects themselves. Useful categories have emerged from the Art Education literature that theorises three tiers of learning, identified as Art-based outcomes, Art-related outcomes and Ancillary outcomes (Eisner, 1998). The first two relate to the art forms and products from artwork, and also encompass aspects of aesthetic appreciation. Ancillary outcomes may be considered to encompass learning in other academic and non-academic areas. A similar in-depth examination of learning outcomes is also applicable to the subject being integrated with art, and indeed to any combination of integrated subjects to ensure that the potential of integration to deepen learning is fully exploited and that integration does justice to both subjects. An issue emerging from the literature is the heterogeneity of criteria with regards to the measurement of success among articles consulted. Studies on language integration tend to focus on successful language learning outcomes, though improvements in numeracy learning outcomes were also noted in studies looking at the integration of mathematics and language (Graham et al. 2018). While all but one study on nutritional education reports improved nutritional knowledge among participating children, many of these reports comprise teacher and pupil reports in interviews (Follong et al., 2021). Positive effects of integrating physical activity with core subjects is noted and supported with experimental data, although this improvement tended to be monodisciplinary in nature and reported as improvements in test scores in the core subject, and in physical activity by increases such as step counts or measures of physical health (Martinnen et. al., 2015). While positive effects of integration of numeracy across the curriculum on some measures are reported from studies in these sources, it may be that appropriate attention to explicitly stated and understood integrated learning goals would have resulted in a stronger focus on integrated outcomes, doing full justice to all subjects integrated. Learning is a complex process of acquiring skills, knowledge and experience, and different disciplinary approaches can support enhanced learning. However, as discussed above, the use of a particular discipline as an instrument or support for learning in another – e.g. mathematics as a vehicle to deliver nutrition content, art as a method for mathematical exploration or physical activity as a way to boost mathematics can diminish the learning in both subjects unless care is taken to balance the aims of both disciplines and avoid superficial treatment of either (Ahlskog-Björkman & Björklund, 2016).

Subject- and Content-based Integration: Challenges

While many examples in the literature focus on the potential for enhanced learning or deepening and contextualising learners' understanding, integration can be seen as a vehicle to allocate teaching time to an area perceived to be lower on a list of priorities – often in a context of a focus on core subjects or performance on standardised tests. This approach does not guarantee success. Follong et al. (2021), in their analysis of the integration of nutrition education with core subjects in 39 studies in eight countries, point to time-pressure in the school day and advocate the integration of nutrition studies with core subjects as a way to address this important subject. However, despite an explicit focus on the integration of nutrition education with core subjects as a means to access instructional time, only one study met recommended time requirements for nutrition programmes. Similar pragmatic considerations are presented by Martinnen et al. (2015) as a way to increase scores in standardised tests and to ensure PE is given time in a curriculum that prioritises core subjects defined in this study as mathematics and language arts as described above. As such, findings show a reduction of the breadth of physical education to measures of physical activity when PE was integrated in the mathematics lesson, and apparent lower-order treatment of mathematics in the PE lesson. This might be considered to point to an absence of respect for the academic status of the disciplines (McKinney et al., 2014).

In their report on the implementation of the cross-curricular integration of numeracy in post-primary schools in Australia, Carter et al. (2014) point to a number of issues with parallels in the Irish system. As in Ireland, Australia sees calls from the policy level to embed literacy and numeracy across the curriculum, with numeracy defined broadly as “recognising and understanding the role of mathematics in the world and having the dispositions and capacities to use mathematical knowledge and skills purposefully” (ACARA, 2014, as cited in Carter et al. (2014)). Schools are responsible for interpreting, devising and implementing this integration themselves. Varying conceptualisations of numeracy and integration were found among teaching and management staff and acted as a barrier to effective implementation. Confusion as to who bore responsibility for the integrated approach to numeracy was observed, with non-specialist mathematics teachers seeing it as belonging to mathematics teachers. Mathematics teachers in turn conceptualised numeracy as the application of mathematical skills in other subjects and therefore the responsibility of teachers of those subjects. A view of numeracy as an add-on rather than an integral part of a

lesson was observed as a barrier to effective integration, as did demands on teachers' time to plan for and evaluate the numeracy element. These findings indicate that system-wide support is necessary. A commitment to cross-curricular numeracy by appropriate authorities should be reflected in curriculum documentation and formal assessment procedures. In addition, there is evidence of the need for support from an engaged management team at school level.

Discussion

It can be seen from our outline of findings that, while various models of integration have much potential for the holistic development of the learner and for deepening understanding of component subject areas, there are many challenges that need to be addressed if integration is to be implemented in an effective way. Below we address each research question on the basis of the review conducted.

What benefits potentially accrue to integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?

While significant time and effort must be invested in an integrated approach to teaching and learning, benefits are seen in the literature. There is evidence that the more traditional outcomes as assessed by teacher-designed and more standardised tests are well served, and the suggestion that, done well, powerful connections can be made within and between subjects with numeracy competence applied and developed. Moreover, there are benefits in integrating history, social justice and maths; nutrition and numeracy among others. As seen in some of the STEM/STEAM education examples there are improvements in a range of "non-traditional" outcomes such as such as the use of real-world contexts in teaching and learning, increased student collaboration, as well as the provision of opportunities for community involvement.

Problem- and project-based learning as well as problem posing - which have been found to have cognitive, affective and interpersonal benefits - are strongly endorsed as an approach to integration that supports high-quality learning. Problems can vary from highly unstructured to more structured examples. It is important that problems that (a) are meaningful and relevant to learners' lives, and that (b) require the application of mathematical skills in the solution process, are sourced or developed. These problems can

emanate from the community, from other subjects of the curriculum as well as from mathematics itself (Askew, 2015; Bennison, 2015; White & Delaney, 2021).

What factors underpin effective integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?

In order for effective integration of numeracy to occur, some key requirements need to exist at a school and indeed at a system level. As discussed by Belbase et al. (2021), lack of understanding about the meaning of STEM can lead to confusion over the focus of an integrated approach to teaching and learning. The same appears to be true about the meaning of numeracy. Messages from Carter et al. align with the view on the need for all involved staff members to reach a shared and understood consensus on what numeracy is. There is a danger that numeracy is perceived by teachers and society at large from a “basic-skills” perspective and this can lead to superficial integration such as the recording of simple data described by Martinnen (2015). Current understandings of numeracy as embracing “problem-solving” and “critical” orientations are important in helping young people to deepen their understanding of some of the societal issues that they encounter. McGee and Hostetler (2014), for example, provide a range of examples from social justice contexts such as voter enfranchisement, systematic inequalities in justice systems, and others. The successful implementation of examples such as these depends on the development and sharing of ideas around the nature and purpose of meaningful integration of numeracy. In addition, McKinney et al. (2014) identify a number of prerequisites for integrated learning, including commitment from management to the ideas and principles of such learning, a recognition among teachers of the academic status of different subjects, an openness to communicate with other disciplines and value cross-curricular work, eschewing notions of disciplinary superiority and status. An understanding of the concepts, skills and processes of the other disciplines is required, as is time and opportunity to develop this understanding. All of these requirements require resources, attention and commitment.

This complex work of planning, teaching and assessing requires support at all levels of the educational system. The work of developing understandings of the integration process - particularly transdisciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches which are endorsed in the literature - is considerable. Coupled with this is the need for teachers to develop understandings of disciplines with which they are not familiar or not comfortable. The provision of appropriate support materials and formal professional development opportunities

for all schools would facilitate engagement with these processes. It is likely, for example, that teachers would welcome support materials such as exemplars of good planning and good teaching for integration, and opportunities to consult and be consulted. Collaborative and local professional development actions bring considerations of the allocation of time and space in the school building and calendar and require an engaged and committed school leadership to prioritise and support integration.

What are the challenges to effective integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?

Despite the symbiosis that can exist between subjects, there is a danger in the enactment of cross-curricular numeracy that one subject is overshadowed by another or indeed that one is neglected or treated in a rudimentary fashion. Learning outcomes and learning activities must be carefully planned with regard to their potential to promote learning in all subjects involved. As mentioned above some of these outcomes may extend beyond the cognitive domain to include affective and interpersonal components. This consideration of learning outcomes has implications for assessment practices. For example, formal assessments at primary and post-primary level tend to be monodisciplinary, with an associated impact on teaching. The design of integrated modules across disciplines, taking account of learning in the domains of knowledge, skills and practices is identified as a challenge, as is providing learning experiences allowing students to advance their knowledge and make connections between the areas. Authentic assessment that focuses on evaluating the learners' success in achieving learning intentions is required to form judgements on their learning and on the value and validity of the integrated models or units.

Limitations

The paucity of research literature on numeracy across the curriculum is a particular limitation of this review. Moreover, some of the available literature on integration is relatively sparse and acknowledged to be heterogeneous and in need of more developed theories and more empirical research. The conceptualisation of integration in the various studies received uneven treatment, and in some cases appeared to be superficial in nature. There was limited interrogation of the approach to integration adopted, e.g., transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary, or cross-disciplinary. We expect that as the integration of numeracy is embraced more fully in primary and post-primary schools further research will come on stream and address these shortcomings.

References

- *Aguilera, D., & Ortiz-Revilla, J. (2021). Stem vs. Steam education and student creativity: A systematic literature review. *Education Sciences, 11*(7). Scopus.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11070331>
- Askew, M. (2015). Numeracy for the 21st century: A commentary. *ZDM, 47*(4), 707-712.
- *Belbase, S., Mainali, B. R., Kasemsukpipat, W., Tairab, H., Gochoo, M., & Jarrah, A. (2021). At the dawn of science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics (STEAM) education: Prospects, priorities, processes, and problems. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*. Scopus.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2021.1922943>
- Bennison, A. (2015). Supporting teachers to embed numeracy across the curriculum: A sociocultural approach. *ZDM, 47*(4), 561-573.
- *Carter, M. G., Klenowski, V., & Chalmers, C. (2015). Challenges in Embedding Numeracy throughout the Curriculum in Three Queensland Secondary Schools. *Australian Educational Researcher, 42*(5), 595–611. Eric.
- De Villiers, J. (2015). Taking account of both languages in the assessment of dual language learners. *Seminars in Speech and Language 36*(2), 120-32. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0035-1549107>
- Edmunds, J., Arshavsky, N., Glennie, E., Charles, K., & Rice, O. (2017). The relationship between project-based learning and rigor in STEM-focused high schools. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-Based Learning, 11*(1), article 3. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.7771/1541-5015.1618>
- Eisner, E. W. (1998). Does experience in the arts boost academic achievement? *Art Education, 51*(1), 7–15.
- *Follong, B. M., Verdonschot, A., Prieto-Rodriguez, E., Miller, A., Collins, C. E., & Bucher, T. (2021). Nutrition across the curriculum: A scoping review exploring the integration of nutrition education within primary schools. *Nutrition Research Reviews, 1*–44. Scopus.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0954422421000111>
- *Gao, X., Li, P., Shen, J., & Sun, H. (2020). Reviewing Assessment of Student Learning in Interdisciplinary STEM Education. *International Journal of STEM Education, 7*. Eric.
<https://dcu.idm.oclc.org/login?url=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1256792&site=ehost-live&scope=site>
- Geiger, V., Forgasz, H. & Goos, M. (2015). A critical orientation to numeracy across the curriculum. *ZDM Mathematics Education 47*, 611–624. <https://doi-org.dcu.idm.oclc.org/10.1007/s11858-014-0648-1>

- *Graham, K. M., Choi, Y., Davoodi, A., Razmeh, S., & Dixon, L. Q. (2018). Language and Content Outcomes of CLIL and EMI: A Systematic Review. *Latin American Journal of Content and Language Integrated Learning*, 11(1), 19–37. Eric.
- Harris, J., & O’Duibhir, P. (2011). *Effective language teaching: A synthesis of research. Research Report No. 13*. Dublin: National Council for Curriculum and Assessment.
- Krashen, S. D. (1985). *The input hypothesis: Issues and implications*. New York, NY: Longman.
- *Marttinen, R. H. J., McLoughlin, G., Fredrick III, R., & Novak, D. (2017). Integration and Physical Education: A Review of Research. *Quest (00336297)*, 69(1), 37–49.
- McCoy, S., Smyth, E., & Banks, J. (2012). *The primary classroom: Insights from the growing up in Ireland study*. Dublin: ESRI.
- *McDonald, P. A., & Smith, J. M. (2020). Improving Mathematical Learning in Scotland’s “Curriculum for Excellence” through Problem Posing: An Integrative Review. *Curriculum Journal*, 31(3), 398–435. Eric.
- *McGee, E. O., & Hostetler, A. L. (2014). Historicizing Mathematics and Mathematizing Social Studies for Social Justice: A Call for Integration. *Equity & Excellence in Education*, 47(2), 208–229.
- *McKinney, S., Hall, S., Lowden, K., Smith, M., & Beaumont, P. (2014). Searching for meaning—science and religious education teachers collaborating in interdisciplinary teaching and learning. *Scottish Educational Review*, 46(1), 32-47.
- *Merritt, J., Mi Yeon Lee, Rillero, P., & Kinach, B. M. (2017). Problem-Based Learning in K-8 Mathematics and Science Education: A Literature Review. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-Based Learning*, 11(2), 1–12.
- *Perignat, E., & Katz-Buonincontro, J. (2019). STEAM in practice and research: An integrative literature review. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 31, 31–43. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2018.10.002>
- Sweller, J. (1988). Cognitive load during problem solving: Effects on learning. *Cognitive Science*, 12(2), 257–285. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15516709cog1202_4
- *White, D., & Delaney, S. (2021). Full STEAM ahead, but who has the map for integration? - A PRISMA systematic review on the incorporation of interdisciplinary learning into schools. *LUMAT*, 9(2). Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.31129/LUMAT.9.2.1387>

Author Bios

Thérèse Dooley is Emeritus Associate Professor in Mathematics Education at DCU Institute of Education. One of the lead authors of the NCCA desktop review of research on mathematics education at early-childhood level, she authored an addendum on primary mathematics. She was a member of the STEM Education Review Group that conducted a comprehensive review of STEM Education in Irish schools, and was Chair of the Tenth Conference of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education held in Dublin in 2017. Passionate about learners' development of powerful mathematical thinking, she continues to work, research and publish in the area. More information available https://www.dcu.ie/researchsupport/research-profile?person_id=14624

Miriam Ryan is an Assistant Professor in Mathematics Education, School of STEM Education, Innovation & Global Studies, DCU Institute of Education, Dublin City University. Miriam has an expertise in designing robust mathematical assessment tasks through working on the Prisons Assessment Project. She is experienced in devising high-quality, authentic mathematical problems through co-authoring *Scope*, 2011 – 2019. Miriam also has experience of working in collaboration with primary teachers to design and facilitate self-directed professional development. Her doctoral thesis will examine the role of the immersion teacher in supporting high quality bilingual mathematical practices. More information available https://www.dcu.ie/researchsupport/research-profile?person_id=14632

Appendix

Research Questions

1. What benefits potentially accrue to integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?
2. What factors underpin effective integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?
3. What are the challenges to effective integration of numeracy across primary and post-primary curricula?

Databases

Three databases were searched (a) EBSCO Education Research Complete (b) EBSCO ERIC (c) Scopus. 'Grey' literature was identified through hand searches.

Key Search Terms

("stem education" OR "mathematics education" OR "math* education" Or "math* teaching or numeracy or math* literacy or math*")

AND ("cross-curricular teaching or teaching cross curricular or cross curricular study or cross curricular integration" OR "interdisciplinary learning" OR "integrated learning or integrated learning in the classroom or subject integration" OR "steam or steam learning" Or "integrated learning or integrated learning in the classroom or subject integration"OR "transdisciplinary or multidisciplinary or cross disciplinary or *disciplinary")

AND ("meta-analysis or systematic review or literature review or meta analysis or overview or review or meta-synthesis or meta synthesis")

NOT ("technology or digital or internet or computers or robot or ict")

We narrowed our search to the years 2011 to 2021, English language articles and those that were peer-reviewed. We did not include pre-school or higher education in our search given our focus on primary and post-primary integration. We excluded articles that did not have a research focus and, given the separate report on digital integration with numeracy, those dealing with digital technology.

The search was completed during July and August 2021 and returned 219 articles, reducing to 142 after duplicates were removed. A summary of the selection process is provided in the PRISMA flow diagram overleaf. All articles were screened by both authors independently by referring to the title and abstract to ascertain the likelihood of meeting eligibility criteria. Through this process 98 studies were deemed irrelevant. All potential remaining titles (44) were divided between the two authors and were read fully to establish if they were eligible. 31 studies were excluded due to issues such as lack of applicability to numeracy or integration, irrelevant setting (e.g., higher education), inappropriate study design (e.g., single case study), practitioner (rather than research) focus, philosophical thrust, lack of availability and, in one case, poor quality where there was insufficient data for claims made. 13 studies remained. Supplementary readings (grey literature) were identified by hand searches.

Prisma Chart

Tabulation

Review	No. of studies	Effect size	Focus and age range	Perspective on numeracy	Key Findings
<p>Aguilera, D., & Ortiz-Revilla, J. (2021). Stem vs. Steam education and student creativity: A systematic literature review. <i>Education Sciences</i>, 11(7). Scopus. https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11070331</p>	14	N/A	<p>Potential of STEM/STEAM Education to develop creativity</p> <p>(primary, secondary and tertiary)</p>	Not stated	<p>High degree of ambiguity in conceptualisations of STEM Education and STEAM Education</p> <p>Appears to be a preference among researchers for the Likert-type test to evaluate creativity</p> <p>STEAM Education projects likely to focus on creativity as a process while STEM Education projects more oriented to the final product</p> <p>Both STEM and STEAM education generated positive effects on student creativity; however, evidence for this limited</p>
<p>Belbase, S., Mainali, B. R., Kasemsukpipat, W., Tairab, H., Gochoo, M., & Jarrah, A. (2021). At the dawn of science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics (STEAM) education: Prospects, priorities, processes, and problems. <i>International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology</i>. Scopus. https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2021.1922943</p>	<p>Document analysis: 21 websites; 30 books or chapters; more than 20 journal articles;</p> <p>seven conference proceeding; two doctoral</p>		<p>Current state of STEAM Education: STEAM movement, purpose and benefits</p> <p>(primary, secondary and tertiary)</p>	<p>Mathematics as intimate connection to science, engineering, and arts</p>	<p>Internationally, direction of STEM/STEAM initiatives is towards an integrated pedagogy</p> <p>Problem-based learning and problem-solving scenarios an effective means of implementing STEAM Education</p> <p>Assessment of student learning in STEAM Education critical; student-centred, holistic and criterion-based approaches seem most appropriate</p> <p>Critiques include dominance of some subjects over others, complexity of implementation, shallow learning particularly of mathematics.</p>

	dissertations				Prerequisites: respect among teaching colleagues of value of different disciplines and of integrated approach; teacher knowledge; time for preparation and training; resources/space
Carter, M. G., Klenowski, V., & Chalmers, C. (2015). Challenges in Embedding Numeracy throughout the Curriculum in Three Queensland Secondary Schools. <i>Australian Educational Researcher</i> , 42(5), 595–611. Eric. <u>DOI: 10.1007/s13384-015-0188-x</u>	N/A	N/A	Numeracy (post-primary)	Application of mathematical skills in the context of other subject areas	Various definitions of numeracy, both explicit and implicit, in use within schools A need for common understandings of numeracy and integration to be developed among teachers, time demands, ownership of integration and a need for CPD emerged as key issues
Graham, K. M., Choi, Y., Davoodi, A., Razmeh, S., & Dixon, L. Q. (2018). Language and Content Outcomes of CLIL and EMI: A Systematic Review. <i>Latin American Journal of Content and Language Integrated Learning</i> , 11(1), 19–37. Eric. <u>DOI:10.5294/laclil.2018.11.1.2</u>	25	N/A	CLIL	Not stated	Learners in a CLIL environment generally achieve at equivalent or higher levels than their peers in first language environments Consideration given to the complexities of authentic assessments in CLIL environments Very small number of studies (2/25) considered mathematics
Follong, B. M., Verdonshot, A., Prieto-Rodriguez, E., Miller, A., Collins, C. E., & Bucher, T. (2021). Nutrition across the curriculum: A scoping review exploring the integration of nutrition education within primary schools. <i>Nutrition Research Reviews</i> , 1–44.	39	N/A	Nutrition Education	Not stated	A scoping review of the practices and results of integrating nutrition with core subjects - often but not exclusively mathematics, literacy, and/or science. Rationales for integrating literacy include ensuring nutrition is addressed by integrating it with core subjects, providing contexts for core subjects, and improving outcomes in both areas. Heterogenous approaches, durations and outcomes hinder

Scopus. DOI: 10.1017/S0954422421000111					evaluation of programmes, though teacher-reported evaluations of programmes generally positive
Gao, X., Li, P., Shen, J., & Sun, H. (2020). Reviewing Assessment of Student Learning in Interdisciplinary STEM Education. <i>International Journal of STEM Education</i> , 7. Eric. DOI: 10.1186/s40594-020-00225-4	49	N/A	STEM Education (post-primary)	Not stated	Focus on assessment of STEM modules Mismatch between assessment and learning, with monodisciplinary, product- focused assessments of interdisciplinary, process focused learning noted Apparent deficiencies in reporting impede rich conclusions in this area Interdisciplinary practices reveal the assessment practices to be complex and time consuming
Marttinen, R. H. J., McLoughlin, G., Fredrick III, R., & Novak, D. (2017). Integration and Physical Education: A Review of Research. <i>Quest</i> (00336297), 69(1), 37–49. DOI: 10.1080/00336297.2016.1150864	23	N/A	Physical Education (PE)	Performance on standardized tests	Theorises that the integration of physical education of physical activity with assessed core subjects (mathematics and language arts) will improve assessment outcomes Findings include positive outcomes for providing contexts for core subjects, for increased activity levels and for student motivation. Heterogeneous studies available, which did not address measurable outcomes in core subjects.
McDonald, P. A., & Smith, J. M. (2020). Improving Mathematical Learning in Scotland’s “Curriculum for Excellence” through Problem Posing: An Integrative Review. <i>Curriculum Journal</i> , 31(3), 398–435. Eric. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1002/curj.15	20	N/A	Mathematical problem-posing (primary, post-primary and initial teacher education (ITE)	Mathematics as centrally important to daily living, emphasis on problems that are meaningful to learners	Improvement in mathematical achievement was reported for both primary and post-primary students Largest effect sizes for primary pupils were found for increased engagement, motivation and creativity. At secondary level, large effect sizes for increased academic achievement.

					<p>Problem-posing interventions can improve both problem-posing and problem-solving skills</p> <p>Importance of group work and reflection noted</p> <p>Some difficulties encountered, e.g., inability to pose contextualised or sensible problems</p>
<p>McGee, E. O., & Hostetler, A. L. (2014). Historicizing Mathematics and Mathematizing Social Studies for Social Justice: A Call for Integration. <i>Equity & Excellence in Education</i>, 47(2), 208–229.</p> <p><u>DOI: 10.1080/10665684.2014.900428</u></p>	N/A	N/A	Integration of mathematics and social justice/ history	Some aspects of mathematics, such as descriptive and analytical statistics as a powerful tool to support the interrogation of social issues	A call to integrate mathematical skills and approaches to analyse, evaluate and appraise current and historical issues of social justice such as quantitatively evaluating social and economic issues relating to the ‘war on drugs’, and statistical approaches to issues of voter disenfranchisement
<p>McKinney, S., Hall, S., Lowden, K., Smith, M., & Beaumont, P. (2014). Searching for meaning–science and religious education teachers collaborating in interdisciplinary teaching and learning. <i>Scottish Educational Review</i>, 46(1), 32-47.</p>	N/A	N/A	Integration of science and religion	Not stated	<p>A study into the practical and procedural implications for school staffs in implementing quality integration in science and religion</p> <p>Emerging priorities included a need for: support from school leadership; the acquisition of relevant knowledge on the part of the teachers; and the existence of a planning, collaboration and collegiality among contributing teachers</p>
<p>Merritt, J., Mi Yeon Lee, Rillero, P., & Kinach, B. M. (2017). Problem-Based Learning in K-8 Mathematics and Science Education: A Literature Review. <i>Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-Based Learning</i>, 11(2), 1–12.</p> <p><u>DOI:10.7771/1541-5015.1674</u></p>	9	N/A	Problem-based learning (PBL) in Science and Mathematics (K-8)	Conceptual development through problem-based and project-based approaches	PBL interventions designed in all nine studies seem to be divided into two perspectives: “students as active learners” and “teachers as facilitators.” PBL has positive effects on students’ academic achievement, knowledge retention, conceptual development, and attitudes.

					Limitations: some inconsistency in how PBL is conceptualised in studies; most studies involved students in K6-8; all studies focused on science and not mathematics
Perignat, E., & Katz-Buonincontro, J. (2019). STEAM in practice and research: An integrative literature review. <i>Thinking Skills and Creativity</i> , 31, 31–43. Scopus. <u>DOI: 10.1016/j.tsc.2018.10.002</u>	44 (articles)	N/A	Examination of underlying assumptions and approaches to STEAM Education (primary, secondary and tertiary)	Where mathematics is mentioned, it is generally as problem solving	Purpose of STEAM Education: engaging students in STEM learning, developing students' creativity, or as a means for enhancing problem-solving skills in real-world settings STEAM Education characterized by 4 main types of disciplinary integration: transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multi-disciplinary, and cross-disciplinary (former two most conducive to integrated learning) Arts in STEAM is conceived in a myriad of ways Creativity frequently mentioned as outcome of STEAM Education (but not as measured outcome) Generally a lack of explanation of arts education learning outcomes
White, D., & Delaney, S. (2021). Full STEAM ahead, but who has the map for integration? - A PRISMA systematic review on the incorporation of interdisciplinary learning into schools. <i>LUMAT</i> , 9(2). Scopus. <u>DOI: 10.31129/LUMAT.9.2.1387</u>	11	N/A	STEM/STEAM Education and its impact on student learning (Secondary (High School))	Real world problem solving implicit in thrust of article Reference made to STEM literacy	Implementation of STEM/STEAM results in improvement in assessed learning outcomes and can potentially enhance a range of other outcomes not measured by traditional means. Use of project/problem-based learning and community collaboration and involvement are common educational threads for successful implementation